

Deformation and Fracture of Hydrogel Spheres in Diametral Compression

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Abstract

Experimental and simulated mechanical behavior of water saturated hydrogel spheres loaded in diametral compression is reported and analyzed. The measured and modeled parameters include axial force, transverse shape, and deformed volume as functions of imposed diametral displacement. The model is implemented in finite element analysis as a bi-phasic poroelastic material at large deformations. Agreement between the experimental measurements and prior observations of hydrogel and elastomer sphere deformation is demonstrated for force, shape, and volume. In particular, deformation at constant volume for both hydrogels and elastomers is demonstrated experimentally. Agreement between experimental and simulated behavior is demonstrated, providing validation of the model parameters. Analysis shows that stresses in the solid component of the deformed spheres do not vary significantly with imposed displacement rate and are dominated by displacement dependent global axial compression and equatorially localized transverse tension. The results are used to interpret the observed rate-dependent variations in failure force of hydrogel spheres in terms of near-invariant underlying strength of the hydrogel solid component. The combined experimental and analytical methods described provide a clear foundation for measuring fundamental hydrogel mechanical properties.

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1 Introduction

Hydrogels consist of sparse, but three-dimensionally interconnected, networks of cross-linked polymer chains encapsulating a large number of water molecules in the liquid state [1, 2]. The volume fraction of water (the “hydro” component) in a hydrogel is often greater than 99 % such that the volume fraction of the polymer network (the “gel” component) is very small, less than 1 %, and volume expansion ratios from a dry polymer state to a completely saturated hydrogel state can thus be much greater than 100. An example of hydrogel swelling is shown in figure 1. On the left are dry poly(acrylamide)-poly(acrylate) gel beads, diameter $3.10 \text{ mm} \pm 0.05 \text{ mm}$. On the right is a single bead consisting of swollen gel, fully saturated by immersion in de-ionized water for approximately 72 h, forming a bead of near-spherical geometry with diameter $D = 17.5 \text{ mm} \pm 0.5 \text{ mm}$ (here and throughout, unless otherwise noted, quantities are specified as mean \pm standard deviation of experimental measurements). The beads (Carolina Biological Supply Company, Burlington, NC) are identical to those studied by James et al. in a recent work considering saturated gel sphere strength [3]. The kinetics of gel sphere swelling have been measured in detailed studies that also consider the associated physics and mathematics of gel swelling [4, 5].

As a consequence of the behavior depicted in figure 1, hydrogel materials have great potential for application in many technologies requiring localized and controlled liquid storage and transfer. In operation, devices containing hydrogels can absorb or release liquids, often selectively, many times the volume of the hydrogel component. Potential is particularly clear in bioengineering [1, 2, 6–8] but also in agriculture and soft robotics [9, 10]. The large water fractions in hydrogels lead to great biocompatibility and hence potential as tissue engineering scaffolds, cell encapsulates, or drug delivery vehicles in bioengineering. However, the sparse polymer fractions lead to often limiting mechanical properties, as hydrogels are typically extremely compliant, exhibiting elastic moduli $E \leq 100 \text{ kPa}$, and extremely weak, exhibiting failure stresses $\leq 300 \text{ kPa}$. In order to take advantage of the liquid capture abilities, many microstructural modification schemes have been implemented to improve the mechanical properties of base or “conventional” hydrogel materials composed of single polymer networks. Examples of such conventional hydrogels include those formed by poly(acrylamide), poly(ethylene glycol), or biological macromolecules such as agar or gelatin. The microstructural modifications generate “advanced” hydrogels, including double network gels with sacrificial networks [11], and composite gels, with particle or fiber reinforcements [12, 13]. The mechanical behavior of advanced gels is commonly distinguished from conventional gels by increased failure strains and consequent increased works of failure [14]—some advanced hydrogels may exhibit engineering failure strains ≥ 10 .

In addition to a diversity of hydrogel modification schemes, a range of test methods has been implemented to assess hydrogel mechanical properties. These methods include: (i) those focused on small-scale deformation, such as rheometry [15] and, particularly, indentation [16–23]; (ii) those focused on large-scale deformation and failure, such as conventional homogeneous tension [24, 25] and compression [26, 27] geometries, as well as spherical compression [3, 28, 29]; and (iii) those focused on fracture, such as the trouser tear [30] and planar tension [31–33] geometries (the latter is commonly referred to as “pure shear” when applied to elastomers [34]). The range of methods has enabled a broad picture of hydrogel mechanical properties to emerge, including assessments of microstructural effects, such as those giving rise to the large failure strains noted above and the lack of gross specimen plasticity associated with hydrogel fracture. Deformation in most hydrogel components is characterized by nonlinear elasticity reflecting the interconnected rubber-like structure and large strains [35], with superposed time-dependence arising from viscoelastic [36] or poroelastic [37] effects, or both [16].

However, as highlighted in a recent Perspective [14], in order to guide development of hydrogel mi-

crostructures for specific applications, measurements of hydrogel mechanical behavior are required in greater quantitative detail. In addition, the Perspective noted that for many applications, especially biomedical, mechanical characterization of hydrogel materials in nontraditional shapes (i.e., beyond tensile bars) is required. The work here addresses these requirements and extends the range of quantitative mechanical test methods applicable to hydrogels. In particular, the work provides a detailed experimental and analytical investigation of the deformation and fracture of hydrogel spheres in diametral compression. The work builds on two experimental foundations: (i) the recent work of James et al. that considered diametral compression and failure of saturated poly(acrylamide)-poly(acrylate) hydrogel spheres [3]; and (ii) the recent works of Offedu et al. and Islam and Oyen that considered time-dependent force relaxation of saturated hydrogel surfaces on spherical indentation [21–23]. James et al. noted nonlinear load-displacement behavior on deformation prior to failure and increases in the mean values and dispersion of failure forces with increased imposed displacement rates. Offedu et al. and Islam and Oyen obtained poroelastic mobility parameters (diffusivity, permeability) characterizing the time-dependent deformation.

Here, new experimental observations are presented for both axial and transverse deformation on loading and a model of diametral compression of a hydrogel sphere using finite element analysis (FEA) is developed. The model implements a large deformation nonlinear elastic response coupled with poroelastic behavior and uses the experimental deformation parameters. The model is used to interpret sphere failure forces as hydrogel strengths. Background and context for the new experimental observations and the model results are provided by comparison with prior elastomer and hydrogel observations. Specifically, force-displacement and exterior profile information from prior works was obtained by digitizing and analyzing published plots and images and (infrequently) from published tables [3, 28, 29, 38–52]. The next sections describe the experimental and analytical methods used here. These are followed by presentation of experimental deformation observations, the modeled stress results, and, finally, the combination of the prior failure observations [3] with the stress results to generate strength data. The results are discussed in terms of the strength behavior of advanced hydrogels.

2 Methods

2.1 Experimental

Dry polymer spheres of poly(acrylamide)-K poly(acrylate), identical to those studied earlier [3], were obtained from Carolina Biological Supply Company (Burlington, NC). Prior to mechanical testing the dry spheres were immersed in distilled water for 5 days at room temperature, during which time the spheres absorbed water and swelled to a saturated hydrogel sphere diameter D of approximately 17.5 mm, radius $R = D/2 = 8.75$ mm, figure 2(a). The solid fraction of the hydrogel spheres was approximately 0.0055 by volume [3]. Uniaxial diametral compression tests were performed in air on the saturated hydrogel spheres using a universal mechanical testing machine and two 50 mm co-axial stainless steel platens. The lower platen was fixed and the displacement of the upper platen was controlled, compressing the hydrogel spheres until rupture. The required force P as a function of displacement w was monitored during loading, both positive directed into the sphere, setting $P = w = 0$ at initial contact. As the system was symmetric, the contact displacement δ at each pole of a sphere was equal and $w = 2\delta$, figure 2(b). Videos of the transverse profiles of the spheres were recorded during loading, enabling both the contact radius a and equatorial radius b to be determined as a function of w for the deformed spheres, figure 2(b). For an ideal sphere, $a = 0$ and $b = R$ at the start of

the test. In practice, the compliance of the spheres often lead to slight “slumping” into oblate forms under the influence of the gravitational body force arising from the mass of absorbed water. Estimations of this effect were $a/R \leq 0.02$ and $b/R \leq 1.02$. The transverse position of the saturated spheres was sometimes fixed on the lower platen axis with a sandpaper sheet, absorbent tissue, or glue—no significant differences in the mechanical responses were observed. No significant exudation of water from the spheres was observed on compression. Three imposed displacement rates \dot{w} were used, $\dot{w} = 1 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$, 0.1 mm s^{-1} , and 0.01 mm s^{-1} .

An image of a sphere and platens in the initial zero force configuration is shown in figure 3(a). Examples of force-displacement responses for spheres compressed at the three displacement rates are shown in figure 3(b). The responses at all three rates are convex, consistent with the effects of both geometrical and material nonlinearity. For comparison, the geometrically nonlinear Hertzian response for contact by a rigid flat on a linear elastic sphere is $P \sim w^{3/2}$ [53]. Similarly, a comparative material nonlinear response is that for an elastomer in uniaxial compression, for which the modulus approximately doubles at an engineering strain of -0.5 [35] (comparable to that shown). Distinguishing these effects on plots such as figure 3(b) is difficult. In more detail, although there is some variability it is clear that the force-displacement responses observed at the faster displacement rates were greater than those at slower rates. Such rate effects are consistent with force-displacement hysteresis observed during diametral load-unload cycles [28,29] and force relaxation with time during constant diametral displacement [3,28] and, particularly, force relaxation with time during constant indentation displacement [16,17,20–22,54] observed in other hydrogel systems. Finally, it is clear that the failure forces were greater for spheres tested at the faster displacement rates, more than a factor of 2, a major finding of the earlier work [3], although in all cases the failure was brittle with catastrophic force drop on failure. A consequence of the nonlinear force-displacement responses is that the conjugate failure displacements varied only weakly with displacement rate, no more than a factor of 1.15.

2.2 Poroelastic Finite Element Analysis

A three-dimensional poroelastic model of hydrogel sphere deformation was developed using finite element analysis (FEA). Aspects of poroelastic mechanics are first summarized to provide background and context for both the model and its experimental calibration, as well interpretation of subsequent experimental and analytical observations. Detailed analyses can be found elsewhere [37,55,56].

The elastic strain energy density \mathcal{U}_E (energy/volume) in a porous linear elastic solid containing a fluid—here, the hydrogel material—is given by

$$\mathcal{U}_E = G \left[\varepsilon_{ij}\varepsilon_{ij} + \frac{\nu}{1-2\nu}(\varepsilon_{kk})^2 \right] + \frac{K_f \zeta^2}{2}. \quad (1)$$

The first term represents the strain energy in the solid, where (G, ν) are the shear modulus and Poisson’s ratio, respectively, of the drained solid. The second term represents the strain energy in the fluid, where K_f is the bulk modulus of the fluid. ε_{ij} is strain in the solid and the Einstein repeated index summation convention is used. ζ is the variation of fluid volume relative to that of a hydrogel material element. Stress is given by partial differentiation of the energy density with respect to strain, $\sigma_{ij} = \partial \mathcal{U}_E / \partial \varepsilon_{ij}$, such that the “effective stress” in the hydrogel material is

$$\sigma_{ij} = 2G \left(\varepsilon_{ij} + \frac{\nu}{1-2\nu} \varepsilon_{kk} \delta_{ij} \right) - \alpha p \delta_{ij}, \quad (2)$$

where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta. $p = -K_f \zeta$ is the pressure (a negative stress) in the fluid and α is a dimensionless geometry coefficient characterizing the volume change of the fluid relative to the volume change of the material element. Mechanical equilibrium is given by setting the summed partial derivatives of the effective stress to zero, $\partial \sigma_{ij,i} = 0$, to give

$$2G \left(\frac{\partial \varepsilon_{kk}}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\nu}{1-2\nu} \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{kk}}{\partial x_i} \right) - \alpha \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} = 0. \quad (3)$$

Re-arranging and assuming that the dilatational strain is homogeneous within a hydrogel material element, $\varepsilon_{kk} = \zeta$, gives

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} = \frac{2G(1-\nu)}{\alpha(1-2\nu)} \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial x_i}, \quad (4)$$

This equation connects the pressure and volume change gradients in the fluid in the constraining presence of the solid.

Conservation of fluid requires that the time rate of fluid volume change within a material element to be balanced by the sum of flux spatial gradients,

$$\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial J_i}{\partial x_i}, \quad (5)$$

where J_i is a fluid flux (rate of fluid volume passing through an area). Fluid flux is related to pressure gradient by Darcy's law

$$J_i = -\frac{k}{\mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i}, \quad (6)$$

where k is the permeability of the hydrogel to fluid flow and μ is the viscosity of the fluid. Combining Eq. (4), (5), and (6) gives

$$\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial t} = c \nabla^2 \zeta \quad (7)$$

or

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} = c \nabla^2 p, \quad (8)$$

where the consolidation coefficient c is given by

$$c = \frac{2(1-\nu) Gk}{(1-2\nu) \alpha \mu}. \quad (9)$$

Equations (7) and (8) have the familiar form of diffusion equations and c of Eq. (9) plays the role of a diffusivity. The interpretation of these equations is that a perturbation in the local relative volume or pressure of fluid, ζ or p , is “diffused” away by transport of the fluid through the deforming and permeable solid, or that deformation of the solid creating such perturbations is accommodated by fluid flow. Stiff, permeable solids and small viscosity fluids speed this transport and accommodation. The dimensions of c are those of all diffusivity terms $[c] = \text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$, and it is noted that c involves both equilibrium and transport parameters (for homogeneous fluids c can be interpreted as a self-diffusion coefficient). Equations (7) and (8) are rarely used directly as solving the partial differential equations to meet suitable boundary conditions is very difficult (and more detailed analysis adds terms [55]). However, these equations are used to motivate the idea that the characteristic length scale L for fluid motion in time t in a poroelastic system is $L \sim (ct)^{1/2}$.

A poroelastic FEA model of hydrogel spheres was developed in FEBio studio (version 1.0.0, Salt Lake City, UT). The model was axisymmetric for one fourth of a hydrogel sphere, implemented with two perpendicular

mirror symmetry planes, figure 4(a). The compression platens were represented as rigid planes and contact between the planes and hydrogel surface was modeled as frictionless rigid contact (facet-to-facet contact with the augmented Lagrangian method). The hydrogel surface outside the contact was set to free draining boundary conditions. The FEA model of the hydrogel was meshed using 5963 tetrahedral elements and modeled as a fluid-filled biphasic material as described above with an important difference: The constitutive response of the solid phase, the first term in Eq. (1), was represented as an Ogden hyperelastic material, described by

$$\mathcal{W}_{\mathbf{E}} = (c_p/2)(J - 1)^2 + \sum_{j=1}^N (c_j/m_j^2)(\lambda_1^{m_j} + \lambda_2^{m_j} + \lambda_3^{m_j} - 3 - m_j \ln J), \quad (10)$$

where $\mathcal{W}_{\mathbf{E}}$ is the strain energy function defined in terms of principal stretches $(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3)$. J is the determinant of the deformation gradient tensor. c_p and c_j are material elastic moduli and m_j is a material exponent. The physical meanings of the parameters are interpreted by noting that in the limit of small deformations of a linear elastic material, the first term of Eq. (1) is recovered (using $N = 1$, $m_j = 2$, $c_p = 2G\nu/(1 - 2\nu)$, $c_j = G$, $J = 1 + \varepsilon_{kk}$, and $\lambda_i = 1 + \varepsilon_i$).

3 Results and Analysis

Adaptation of the model parameters to describe experimental observations of sphere compression was performed in two stages. First, the permeability parameter k used in the FEA model was determined. Spherical indentation force relaxation tests were performed on the flat surfaces of halved hydrogel spheres, using a procedure described elsewhere to determine c [17, 18, 22, 23]. The permeability value obtained $k = (44 \pm 9) \text{ nm}^2$ was assumed to be strain invariant and isotropic. Using the viscosity of water $\mu = 0.89 \times 10^{-3} \text{ Pa s}$ gives the hydraulic permeability, $k/\mu \approx 0.05 \text{ mm}^4/\text{N.s}$, and this value was used in most of the FEA simulations. Second, the hyperelastic material parameters c_p , c_j , and m_j were determined. Nonlinear least-squares optimization was performed to fit the FEA model response to a fixed-rate $\dot{w} = 10 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$ experimental load-displacement curve, figure 4(b). The equivalent isotropic elastic parameters in the small deformation limit were $G \approx 60 \text{ kPa}$ and $\nu \approx 0.31$. The FEA solver FEBio (version 2.5) was used to simulate the uniaxial diametral compression behavior of the hydrogel spheres.

Comparison of the experimental and model behavior of the spheres in compression is thence shown in figure 5. Figure 5(a) shows an experimental image of an undeformed sphere, $w = 0 \text{ mm}$. Figures 5(b), 5(c), and 5(d) show increasing levels of imposed displacement, (b) $w = 1 \text{ mm}$, (c) $w = 3 \text{ mm}$, and (d) $w = 8 \text{ mm}$. There is clearly transverse as well as axial deformation of the sphere. Figure 5(e) shows a simulated model image of an undeformed sphere. Figures 5(f), 5(g), and 5(h) show increasing levels of model imposed displacement, approximating those of the above images. The similarity of the experimental and model images is clear, including the relationship between the axial and transverse displacements and the shapes of the exterior profiles. The following sections use results such as those in figure 5 to examine the experimental and model exterior deformations of the spheres in more detail, including comparisons with related systems. Videos of a sphere compression experiment and a FEA model simulation are given in supplementary material.

3.1 Deformation

Figure 6 shows a logarithmic plot of force-displacement, P - w , behavior for a saturated hydrogel sphere tested at a displacement rate of $\dot{w} = 1 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$. Representative comparative data from other sphere systems

loaded in diametral compression are also shown. For ease of comparison, the data are plotted as force P vs relative displacement w/D . Symbols represent individual observations. Large bold symbols represent hydrogel measurements, small gray symbols represent other systems. The bold solid line represents the fitted hydrogel model results. The fine lines are guides to the eye consistent with linear elastic Hertzian contact behavior, $P \sim w^{3/2}$ (slope 3/2 in logarithmic coordinates). For this plotting scheme, there was negligible difference between the deformation behavior of the hydrogel sphere shown and repeat tests at the same or different displacement rates.

Over much of the displacement domain the hydrogel force behavior is slightly less dependent on displacement than a Hertzian response. At large displacements, the force behavior exhibits a greater dependence on displacement than Hertzian. The second observation is easily explained by material nonlinear effects associated with large deformations and a transition in behavior from Eq. (1) to Eq. (10). This interpretation is supported by comparison with the model behavior that is Hertzian at small displacements and greater than Hertzian as a consequence of hyperelastic effects at large displacements. Although rate and time effects are clear in figure 3(b) and in the cited hysteresis and relaxation studies, such that the measured forces in monotonic deformation tests are likely to be slightly overestimated relative to the equilibrium values, the force and displacement variations with time are negligible relative to the overall deviation from Hertzian behavior in figure 6. The implication is that the hydrogel sphere behavior of figure 6 is associated with a generic feature of hydrogel sphere structure. A possible explanation is that there is a slightly denser outer surface layer that gives rise to stiffening at small displacements. Comparison with other systems supports these interpretations.

The data included in figure 6 from other sources describing diametral compression of spheres are (in order of decreasing supported force) (i) polyurethane rubber, diameter $D = 174$ mm [38], (ii) natural rubber, $D = 10$ mm [42], and (iii) saturated polysaccharide hydrogel, $D = 0.46$ mm [28]. Although the range of forces is large, a factor of 10^7 , the behavior is very similar and the overall Hertzian-like trends are clear. In particular, the polysaccharide hydrogel exhibits a slightly less than Hertzian response at small relative displacements that stiffens towards hyperelastic behavior at large relative displacements. The two rubber materials approach the Hertzian response at small displacements and exhibit deviations towards hyperelastic behavior at large displacements, particularly the natural rubber at displacements approaching the sphere diameter, $w/D \approx 0.8$. Similar behavior (not shown), tending to Hertzian behavior at small relative displacements and hyperelastic behavior at large relative displacements, is exhibited by other systems of various compositions, including hydrogels [3, 44, 47–51], rubber [43, 46], and dense polymers [45, 52].

Figure 7 shows logarithmic plots of the major transverse dimensions, contact radius a and equatorial radius b , figure 2(b), as a function of axial displacement w from experimental observations, figure 7(a), and model simulations, figure 7(b), of saturated hydrogel spheres in diametral compression. Representative comparative data from other sphere systems loaded in diametral compression are also shown in both plots. For ease of comparison, the data are plotted as relative dimensions a/R and b/R vs relative displacement $w/D (= \delta/R)$. Symbols represent individual observations. Large bold symbols represent hydrogel measurements, small gray symbols represent other systems. The hydrogel measurements were determined from video frames, such as in figure 5(a)–(d), for spheres tested at imposed axial displacement rates of $\dot{w} = 1$ mm s⁻¹ and 0.1 mm s⁻¹. The hydrogel model results were determined from simulation outputs, such as those giving rise to figure 5(e)–(h). The fine lines are guides to the eye consistent with linear elastic Hertzian contact behavior, $a \sim w^{1/2}$ (slope 1/2) and $b = 1$.

The results from prior work on other systems included observations on rubber [38, 40, 42, 43, 46] and

hydrogels [3, 29]. The responses tend to Hertzian behaviors at small axial displacements ($w/D \ll 1$) and deviate from these behaviors to significantly larger values at large displacements ($w/D \rightarrow 1$). At such displacements, a and b converge such that the spheres tend to a “pancake” geometry, particularly so for the rubber materials (the extreme data in figure 7 exhibit width to thickness ratios of $\approx 2/0.2 = 10$; see [44] for an example of reversible pancake deformation). The experimental observations for the hydrogel spheres here were similar to the previous observations with two small exceptions. At small and intermediate axial displacement values the hydrogel a and b values were slightly greater than the prior (largely elastomer) values and Hertzian responses. The hydrogel behavior did not extend to large axial displacements as the responses were truncated by sphere fracture and failure, figure 3(b). The model results for the hydrogel spheres were similar to the previous observations, and the experimental observations, including the best fit of figure 4(b). For both the experimental measurements and the model simulations there was no significant effect of imposed displacement rate \dot{w} on deformed sphere aspect ratios, a/w or b/w . Further, comparison with the prior observations suggests that there is no significant effect of material, rubber or hydrogel, on deformed aspect ratios. This shared behavior probably results from a shared constraint of conserved volume on deformation—both rubber and hydrogels appear to be “incompressible” materials. This behavior is well known for rubber [35]. Experimental observations show that negligible water exudes from hydrogel spheres during loading implying that deformation occurs at constant volume. An experimental test of the constant volume hypothesis requires more detailed information regarding deformed sphere profiles.

Figure 8 shows profile data for spheres deformed in diametral compression: (a) Rubber, from digitized published profiles [42] and (b) hydrogel, from digitized images, such as figure 5. For ease of comparison, the data are shown as relative height and width values, z/R and r/R , respectively, using the cylindrical coordinate system shown in figure 9. The profiles are centered for each state of deformation. Symbols represent individual measurements of points on profiles from single sphere experiments. As guides to the eye, the initial sphere profiles are indicated as gray discs and the center symbols in each plot indicate the reported macroscopic positions of the platens for each deformation profile. The four profiles of the four states of deformation shown figure 8(a) indicate the significant widening and flattening of rubber spheres in compression. The taller profile in figure 8(b) indicates the slightly oblate initial shape of an unloaded hydrogel sphere, figures 1, 3(a), and 5(a). The shorter profile indicates the profile of a hydrogel sphere near the limit of deformation prior to failure, figure 5(d). Comparison of figure 8(a) and figure 8(b) makes clear the greater deformation sustainable by a rubber sphere relative to a hydrogel sphere. Figure 8 also makes clear that the exterior profile radii of the deformed spheres for both materials decreased significantly on axial displacement. Similar data (not shown) were observed for other rubber [38, 46] and hydrogel [3, 29] systems.

The contact and equatorial radii a and b mark key points on the full cross-sectional profiles of deformed spheres. In cylindrical polar coordinates (r, z) centered on the sphere with z aligned along the deformation axis, figure 9, the profile of the sphere is given by a relation between z and r . Initially $z^2 + r^2 = R^2$. On deformation, the profile within the contact radius is given by the position of the platen, and thus $z = R - \delta = h$ for $r \leq a$. Exterior to the contact radius, the sphere extends transversely in a curved profile. Figures 5 and 8 suggest that the profile has a characteristic radius less than that of the initial sphere and that the profile meets the platen at an angle greater than zero. A circular profile, figure 9, that meets these constraints is given by

$$(r - c)^2 + z^2 = e^2, \quad a \leq r \leq b, \quad (11)$$

where $(c, 0)$ are the center coordinates of an exterior circular arc of radius e , with $0 \leq c \leq R$ and $h \leq e \leq R$. The arc subtends an angle of 2θ , where $\tan \theta = h/(a - c)$, such that the profile meets the platen at an

angle of $\theta - \pi/2$. The lines shown on the right in each plot in figure 8 represent best fits to each profile of the above shifted circles, treating c and e as unconstrained fitting parameters. The data in each case are clearly well described by such fits. For each system, c increased and e decreased as deformation $w = 2\delta$ proceeded. The angle subtended by the circular arc of each profile was approximately invariant at $2\theta = 120^\circ$, implying invariance in the contact tractions between the spheres and platens. Consideration of the FEA model profiles, figure 5(e)–(h), shows that they are almost ideally described by Eq. (11). The contact and equatorial radii a and b , figure 7, may be used to determine the profiles of figure 8, as consideration of the circular form shows that $c = (b^2 - a^2 - h^2)/2(b - a)$ and $e = b - c$. This information is used below. Other analytical models of deformation profiles are considered in the Discussion.

The volume of the deformed sphere, V , is given by the integral

$$V = 2\pi \int_0^h r^2(z) dz, \quad (12)$$

which is evaluated easily by numerical methods once $r(z)$ is specified. In particular, experimental profiles, as in the $r(z)$ data of figure 8 or $r(z)$ determined from the a and b data of figure 7, can be integrated and compared with initial sphere volumes, $V_0 = 4\pi R^3/3$. Figure 10 shows the results of such calculations for a range of sphere systems, as plots of relative volume V/V_0 vs relative displacement w/D . The central dashed lines in each plot indicate deformation with no changes in volume, $V/V_0 = 1$. The upper and lower dashed lines indicate $V/V_0 = 1.33$ and $V/V_0 = 0.67$, the volume changes of a linear elastic ($\nu = 0.33$) component in uniform uniaxial tension and compression, respectively; the upper and lower boundaries of the plots represent the biaxial extremes. The open symbols in figure 10(a) represent the results of integration by Eq. (12) of experimental profiles of deformed spheres of rubber [38, 42, 46] and a rubber foam [46], and direct determination of cylinder compression results of a gel-derived foam [44]. The filled symbols represent the results of integration by Eq. (12) of experimental profiles of deformed hydrogel spheres generated in prior experiments [3, 29] (taking the initial oblate shapes into account). For all materials, the bars represent uncertainties estimated from profile determinations. The results form two groups. Most of these materials displayed no significant change in volume on diametral compression, $V/V_0 \approx 1$. As anticipated [35] this group included the rubber materials and the hydrogel materials. The foam materials, however, exhibited $V/V_0 < 1$, particularly at large w/D values. The foams decreased in volume significantly on diametral compression, and increased in volume on release—in fact, all materials in figure 10(a) were elastic and recovered, albeit sometimes slowly, on force removal.

The symbols in figure 10(b) represent the results of integration by Eq. (12) of experimental profiles of deformed hydrogel spheres generated in the current experiments (again, taking the initial oblate shapes into account). The bars represent uncertainties estimated from profile determinations. The filled and open symbols represent results from experiments at displacement rates of $\dot{w} = 1 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$ and 0.1 mm s^{-1} , respectively. The results for these hydrogel experiments clearly exhibit a small volume increase, $V/V_0 \approx 1.15$, for $w/D > 0.1$ that is greater for the slower displacement rate tests. The solid lines in figure 10 (b) represent the results of the FEA simulations, analyzed in the same way as the experimental results. The simulations indicate almost no change in volume (implying $J \approx 1$ for the entire sphere). Although the experimental results exhibit a small, consistent, volume deviation from unity, a conclusion from figure 10 is that hydrogel deformation is more rubber-like than foam-like. The positive nature of the deviation, particularly for the slower tests, suggests that volume changes are dominated by tensile stresses and strains within the hydrogel spheres. It is well to note that the relative volume deviation from unity is not much

greater than the uncertainty in the estimated relative volumes, ≈ 0.06 . In addition, the *maximum* relative volume deviation in the experimental results from that of the simulations, ≈ 0.2 , implies that the possible error in strain and thus stress determined by the simulations relative to the experiments is approximately $(1.2^{1/3} - 1) \approx 0.07$. That is, the more constrained simulations could overestimate the stresses in the spheres by approximately 7%. This will be seen to be a very small factor relative to the stress and strength variations examined in the following sections and is less than the relative uncertainty, $\pm 20\%$, in the experimentally determined permeability.

3.2 Stress

Figure 11 shows a sequence of cross-section images of a deformed hydrogel sphere at various imposed displacements w . The exterior shape changes with displacement as shown in figure 5 and discussed in detail in figure 8. The interior stress fields are shown as colored maps of the first invariant of the stress tensor active in the solid, $I = \sigma_{kk} = \sigma_{zz} + \sigma_{rr} + \sigma_{\phi\phi}$ (figure 9; ϕ is a circumferential angular coordinate into the plane of the diagram). On initial displacement, $w = 2$ mm, the stress field appears as zones of overall compression localized to the contacts at the poles of the sphere. As displacement proceeds, $w = 4$ mm, these zones expand in extent, both axially and radially. Faint indication of overall tension appears at the equator of the sphere. On further displacement, $w = 6$ mm, the zones of overall compression merge axially and the equatorial zones of overall tension are clear. In cross section these zones appear separate. For the three-dimensional sphere, the tensile zone is a toroid. The deformation state of the sphere has transformed from two isolated contact events to a compressed column-like structure. The relative displacement in this state is $w/D = 6/17 \approx 0.3$, the value at which the exterior profile begins to markedly deviate from Hertzian contact behavior, figures 6 and 7. The final displacement, $w = 8$ mm, makes clear that the stress state of the deformed sphere is dominated by a central column of overall compressive stress but has a significant surrounding toroidal region of overall tensile stress. (For ease of visualization, the maps extend to $I = \pm 16$ kPa. I values of greater magnitude appear as the bounding shades.)

Figure 12 examines the stress field in the solid in more detail for the final deformation state $w = 8$ mm. The principal stress components, σ_1 , σ_2 , σ_3 , are shown, using the same scale as figure 11 and following convention that numerically $\sigma_1 > \sigma_2 > \sigma_3$. The symmetry of the system here gives $\sigma_1 \approx \sigma_{\phi\phi}$, $\sigma_2 \approx \sigma_{rr}$, and $\sigma_3 \approx \sigma_{zz}$. The dominant principle stress component is $\sigma_3 < 0$, consistent with figure 11, quantifying axial compression σ_{zz} . The toroidal zone of tension from figure 11 is seen to arise from principal stress component σ_1 , quantifying circumferential tension $\sigma_{\phi\phi}$. Note that this tension extends into the center of the sphere. As is typically the case, the most variable principle stress component is σ_2 . σ_2 is tensile at the center of the sphere as symmetry requires $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2$ at this point. $\sigma_2 = 0$ at the sphere periphery exterior to the contact, consistent with a normal traction free boundary condition, $\sigma_{rr} = 0$. The tensile components of the stress field form a biaxial distribution, $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 > 0$ at the center of the sphere that reduces to a uniaxial circumferential field, $\sigma_1 > 0$ on the sphere equatorial surface. All three principal stress components are compressive, $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3 < 0$, adjacent to the contacts. These behaviors are consistent with small deformation stress analyses of linear elastic spheres [57, 58].

An important point to note is that the stress maps of figure 11 and figure 12 were invariant with respect to imposed displacement rate \dot{w} . For \dot{w} varying from 10 mm s^{-1} to 0.01 mm s^{-1} there was no discernible difference in the stress field induced in the solid. The stress field distributions and magnitudes depended entirely on w . However, the supported force P depended significantly on imposed displacement rate. Figure 13(a) shows a plot of force P determined from the FEA model, the integral of $(\sigma_{zz} - p)$ over the $z = h$

plane, for three modeled displacement rates $\dot{w} = 1 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$, 0.1 mm s^{-1} , and 0.01 mm s^{-1} . The functional dependence of the modeled force on displacement was greater than linear, $P \sim w^{3/2}$, independent of \dot{w} . The amplitude dependence of the modeled force on displacement rate was such that the supported force approximately halved as the rate decreased by a factor of 100 from $\dot{w} = 1 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$ to 0.01 mm s^{-1} (a clear example is at $w = 8 \text{ mm}$). The model results of figure 13(a) are in agreement with the experimental observations of figures 3, 4, and 6. As the stress distribution in the solid was independent of displacement rate, the change in supported force was due entirely to changes in the pressure $p(z = h)$ in the fluid at the contact. As the displacement rate decreased, more time was allowed for fluid flow in the pressure gradients induced in the hydrogel by the imposed displacement (see section 2.2) and thus the pressure and supported force at the contact decreased. Increasing the permeability k had the same effect as decreasing the imposed displacement rate, consistent with Eq. (9). Increasing the coefficient of friction at the platen-sphere interface had almost no effect, implying that the contact tractions were almost normal.

Figure 13(b) illustrates the tensile stress fields in the hydrogel spheres at the typical failure displacements observed here, $w = 6 \text{ mm}$, 7 mm , and 8 mm , figure 3(b). As sphere failure is determined by the equivalence of induced stress and sphere strength and the induced stress is independent of the imposed displacement rate, the implication is that sphere strength is deformation rate independent. Slowly loaded spheres thus fail in a state resembling the lower diagram in figure 13(b) and rapidly loaded spheres fail in a state resembling the upper diagram. However, sphere strength is assessed by the peak supported force. For most spheres, figures 3, 4, and 6, supported force varies with displacement as $P \sim \alpha(\dot{w})(w/D)^{3/2}$, where $\alpha(\dot{w})$ is a dimensionless parameter that depends on displacement rate. Here, $\alpha(\dot{w}) \sim \ln \dot{w}$. The model results show that the maximum tensile stress varies with displacement as $\sigma \sim w^{3/2}$. Combining these relationships gives $\sigma \sim P/\alpha(\dot{w})$. As α increases with increasing \dot{w} , a fixed range of observed failure forces corresponds to a smaller domain of sphere strengths as imposed displacement rate is increased. Calibration from the model here gives $\alpha(\dot{w} = 1) \approx 0.87 \text{ MPa/N}$, $\alpha(\dot{w} = 0.1) \approx 0.58 \text{ MPa/N}$, and $\alpha(\dot{w} = 0.01) \approx 0.47 \text{ MPa/N}$.

3.3 Strength

Figure 14(a) is a plot of the failure force empirical distribution functions $Pr(F)$ for hydrogel spheres tested at three imposed displacement rates from the work of James et al. [3] (the data have been lightly censored to remove a few errant small force failures). As noted, the force distributions decreased as the displacement rate decreased. Some of the spheres loaded at the fastest rates failed at supported forces as great as 70 N, although the imposed displacements were only approximately 10 mm, a consequence of the nonlinear $P \sim w^{3/2}$ variation. Figure 14(b) is plot of the strength empirical distribution functions $Pr(\sigma)$ for the spheres, obtained using the above α terms. The symbols are identical to those in figure 14(a) and the shaded bar indicates the strength uncertainty for the $\dot{w} = 0.1 \text{ mms}^{-1}$ data set estimated from the stress maps and force determinations (figures 12 and 13); uncertainties for the other sets are similar. The well separated failure force responses are collapsed into very close strength distribution responses that exhibit very little effect of imposed displacement rate and a common lower bound strength threshold. Within experimental uncertainty, the strengths of these hydrogel spheres is almost displacement rate invariant and figure 14(b) can be regarded as the strength of the hydrogel.

To place the results of figure 14(b) in perspective, figure 15 (a) shows in semi-logarithmic coordinates a ranked distribution of hydrogel strengths compiled in the recent perspective [14]. A striking feature of the distribution is the large strength domain, a factor of nearly 10^4 has been reported for hydrogel strengths, although the median strength of approximately 100 kPa for conventional single network hydrogels is clear.

The shaded band in figure 15(a) indicates the domain of advanced hydrogels, (600–3000) kPa. As noted in the Introduction, the increases in strength from conventional to advanced hydrogels have been achieved by microstructure development. An example of strength increase by microstructure development is shown in figure 15(b) from the tensile strength measurements of Tonsomboon et al. [30]. The plot is a histogram of strengths of composite alginate hydrogels reinforced with gelatin fibers of various orientations. The semi-logarithmic strength scale and shaded bar are repeated from figure 15(a). The open bar (0) represents the strength of the unreinforced material (similar to that considered here). The hatched bars represent the strengths of composite materials with fibers oriented (1) perpendicular to the applied stress on testing, (2) randomly, (3) perpendicular and parallel in laminated plies, and (4) parallel to the applied stress. The significant increase in strength arising from microstructural manipulation, well into the domain of advanced hydrogels is clear. The strength increase on displacement rate variation for a single network hydrogel is shown in figure 15(c) using data from figure 14(b). The semi-logarithmic strength scale and shaded bar are repeated from figure 15(a) and the symbols represent medians and ranges. It is clear that kinetic effects associated with variations in applied displacement rate are no-where near as significant as microstructural effects in altering strength. It is also noted that microstructural manipulation appears to decrease relative strength variability, whereas kinetic effects appear to have a weakly increasing effect on relative strength variability. The predominant effect of microstructure over kinetics in determining brittle fracture strength has been measured and analyzed in ceramic and glass materials for some time, including the differing effects on strength variability [59].

4 Discussion and Conclusions

This work has presented an extensive quantitative assessment of the deformation and fracture of hydrogel spheres loaded in diametral compression. The assessment has included experimental, analytical, and historical perspectives. A major goal of the work, to develop sufficient understanding of hydrogel sphere behavior to interpret compressive failure forces in terms of tensile strengths, has been significantly advanced. The work thus adds another mechanical characterization technique to be used in development of hydrogels for engineering applications, but also places the physical behavior of hydrogels in a broader materials science context.

In regard to this last point, an experimental finding of this work is that hydrogel spheres behave much as rubber and elastomer spheres in diametral compression: the force-displacement behavior is very similar, as are the deformed external profiles, figures 6, 7, and 8. Underlying these similarities is the finding that hydrogel spheres deform at near-constant volume, they are classically “incompressible”, much as rubber but not like sponges or foams, figure 10. There is more work required here, as the recent measurements exhibited only near-constant volume, only partial agreement with previous measurements, and a clear rate effect. Nevertheless, the finding provides a clear test for the validity of hydrogel mechanical properties experiments and a potential constraint on constitutive laws and models, $J = 1$, Eq. (10). In earlier mechanics-based analyses by Tatara [39,41] of diametral compression of rubber spheres, volume-conserving deformation behavior was assumed. Elastic analyses using this assumption were used to predict the external transverse profiles of deformed rubber particles and, assuming a particular nonlinear form for the elastic modulus, the axial force-displacement behavior. The analysis essentially reverses the logical order of figure 10 and figures 6 and 7 here, using $V/V_0 = 1$ as a constraint in predicting $r(z)$ and $P(w)$ to provide a full description of the system, including continuous quantitative force and profile behavior over the entire displacement

range. The analysis is complete, but of some complexity, and the results are not in closed form and require iterative numerical solution. From an experimental point of view, this last point is particularly important with regard to the exterior profiles, which appear to be well described by simple circular arcs, Eq. (11), as illustrated in figures 8 and 9. A previous empirical approach to describing the exterior profiles of deformed spheres [46] simplified Eq. (11) by setting $c = 0$ and $e > R$ but was not a good description of observations. A modification of this latter approach using an elliptical profile was more successful, for both compressible and incompressible materials, but was of greater complexity.

The poroelastic deformation model developed here and implemented using FEA was validated by quantitative comparison of predicted results and experimental observations. In particular, comparison of the axial force-displacement responses, figures 4, 6, and 13, and the transverse profiles, figures 5 and 7. These comparisons provide confidence that the modeled stress distributions within the spheres are predicted correctly. The stress component that is of greatest interest with respect to interpretation of brittle failure of hydrogel spheres is the tensile stress, here, as usual, characterized by the first principal stress. For the deformed hydrogel spheres, the boundary of the tensile region of this stress is a disc-like shape that extends transversely across the sphere to the sphere periphery, figures 12 and 13. For an axial displacement of $w = 8$ mm, the model predicted a supported load of approximately 19 N and a maximum, biaxial tensile stress of approximately 22 kPa at the sphere center and a uniaxial tensile stress of 18 kPa at the sphere periphery. The mean engineering compressive stress in the sphere, based on the undeformed sphere dimensions, is $\sigma = 4P/\pi D^2 \approx 84$ kPa. This characteristic stress was used to estimate hydrogel sphere strengths from failure loads by James et al. [3]. The maximum tensile stress at center of the sphere, based on linear elastic deformation, is $\sigma = 0.9P/D^2 \approx 59$ kPa [57], and that at the periphery is $\sigma \approx 0.6P/D^2 \approx 40$ kPa [58]. The first of these was used recently to analyze the strength distributions of hard Al_2O_3 particles [60]. It is important to recognize the potential differences in behaviors and stress distributions of poroelastic and viscoelastic hydrogels. Here, only poroelastic effects were considered, which may have contributed to the weak rate effects observed at the millimeter scale. An interesting comparison would be to the failure behavior under compression of viscoelastic hydrogel (e.g., alginate) spheres [23].

There are several points to note regarding the above stress estimates. First, although the elastic calculations over-estimate the stress values relative to the partially relaxed poroelastic FEA determined values, all are of the same order of magnitude. Second, a decrease in tensile stress from the center to the periphery, but not to zero, is predicted by both elastic and poroelastic calculations. Third, as noted by Shipway and Hutchings [58], this stress decrease implies that surface failure in sphere systems is only likely if surface flaws are much greater in potency than bulk flaws. For brittle materials this is usually the case, as surface contact induced flaws are more potent and strength-controlling than bulk microstructure induced flaws [59]. Here, the permeability measurements of the hydrogel spheres suggested a very small microstructural length scale of tens of nanometers, whereas experience handling the saturated spheres suggested they were extremely prone to often visible surface contact damage. Hence, it is likely that the maximum tensile stress overestimates the strength of the hydrogel spheres (and probably the earlier Al_2O_3 particles) and that the stress at the periphery is a better estimate. Consideration of flaws highlights that much of the analysis recently developed to deconvolute strength distributions such as figure 14(b) into underlying flaw populations [60] is not directly applicable here. Such analysis relies on a clear quantitative relationship between strength and a flaw size (not necessarily a crack length) that is so far absent for hydrogels.

Finally, it is important to note that the analysis here coupled with the high-throughput hydrogel test method demonstrated earlier [3], has enabled important findings regarding hydrogel strengths, encapsulated

in figures 14 and 15: separation of failure force distributions with imposed displacement rate is probably due to variations in fluid pressure and not variations in solid strength, which appears to vary only weakly with rate; rate effects on conventional hydrogel failure are small relative to the effects of microstructural modifications leading to advanced hydrogels. In ceramic materials, the analytical separation of microstructural toughening from non-equilibrium fracture kinetics was enabled by the fact that toughening was distributed and the kinetics characterized reactions local to the crack tip [59]. In hydrogels, such separation is unlikely as the kinetics of relevance appear to be diffusive transport through the microstructure. Further experiments, involving spheres of different sizes, to assess flaw population effects, and loaded at different rates, to assess fracture kinetics effects, are required.

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Figure 1. Photograph of poly(acrylamide)-poly(acrylate) hydrogel spheres: (left) a few dry spheres (right) a single water saturated sphere.

Figure 2. Schematic cross sections of a hydrogel sphere. (a) Undeformed, diameter $D = 2R$. (b) Deformed by axial displacement $w = 2\delta$ and supported force P . Undeformed state shown dashed, deformed state shown as gray area. Contact radius a , equatorial radius b .

Figure 3. (a) Photograph of undeformed hydrogel sphere resting on sandpaper between compression platens. The meniscus at the base of the sphere was generated by residual surface water. (b) Force-displacement responses to failure for three hydrogel spheres at each of three imposed displacement rates exhibiting nonlinear deformation and brittle failure.

Figure 4. (a) Side image of the meshed quarter model of a hydrogel sphere implemented in finite element analysis; mirror symmetry planes are in the plane and perpendicular to the plane of the diagram. (b) Force-displacement responses of hydrogel spheres. Symbols, experiment. Line, model best fit using experimentally determined permeability.

Figure 5. Experimental (upper) and simulated (lower) images of undeformed and deformed hydrogel spheres. (a) $w = 0$ mm, (b) $w = 1$ mm, (c) $w = 3$ mm, and (d) $w = 8$ mm. (e), (f), (g), and (h), corresponding images of simulation exteriors.

Figure 6. Force-relative displacement response of hydrogel and elastomer spheres. Bold symbols and line, hydrogel experiments and model from this work. Gray symbols (i) polyurethane rubber [38], (ii) natural rubber [42], (iii) hydrogel [28]. Gray lines are guides to the eye of slope $3/2$ consistent with linear elastic Hertzian behavior.

Figure 7. Relative transverse dimensions vs axial relative displacement responses of hydrogel and elastomer spheres. (a) Related observation experiments (gray) [3, 29, 38, 40, 42, 43, 46], $\dot{w} = 1 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$ and $\dot{w} = 0.1 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$ observations (bold). (b) Related observation experiments (gray), $\dot{w} = 1 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$ and $\dot{w} = 0.1 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$ FEA model simulations (bold). The lines represent the linear elastic Hertzian responses.

Figure 8. Full profiles (a) deformed elastomer sphere [42] and (b) deformed hydrogel sphere. Symbols, experimental observations. Lines, best fit circular arcs. Gray discs, undeformed sphere profiles.

Figure 9. Cylindrical coordinate system (r, z) used to describe deformed spheres. Schematic cross section of deformed sphere shown in gray, exterior dimensions, a and b , circular arc of exterior profile characterized by center and radius coordinates c and e .

Figure 10. Relative volume vs relative displacement for compressed sphere systems. (a) Previous experimental observations [3, 29, 38, 42, 44, 46]: open symbols, rubbers and foams; filled symbols, hydrogels. (b) Experimental and model hydrogel results from this work: $\dot{w} = 1 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$ (filled symbols) and $\dot{w} = 0.1 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$ (open symbols), FEA model results (lines) $\dot{w} = 1 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$ (upper) and $\dot{w} = 0.1 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$ (lower).

Figure 11. Cross sections of deformed hydrogel spheres showing color-filled maps of the first invariant of the stress tensor (trace) determined from the FEA model at axial displacements indicated. On deformation, the system progresses from two contact events to a compressed column.

Figure 12. Cross sections of a deformed hydrogel sphere showing color-filled maps of the principal stress components determined from the FEA model. Note the localization of tension in the deformed sphere to the center and periphery.

Figure 13. (a) Plot of supported force vs displacement for hydrogel spheres determined from the FEA model at various imposed displacement rates \dot{w} indicated. (b) Cross sections of a deformed hydrogel sphere showing color-filled maps of the first principal stress component determined from the FEA model at the imposed displacements w indicated. Note that both supported force and resultant stress depend on imposed displacement, but only force depends on displacement rate.

Figure 14. (a) Failure force empirical distribution function (edf) responses of hydrogel spheres from James et al. [3] at displacement rates indicated. (b) Strength edf responses determined using FEA model calibration. Note that the separated force responses collapse to almost rate invariant strength responses.

Figure 15. Aspects of strength behavior of hydrogel materials summarized in three panels. (a) The broad range of reported strengths of hydrogels ranked [14]. The strength of “advanced” hydrogels is indicated by the shaded band and repeated throughout. (b) Strengths of fiber composite hydrogels as a function of microstructure; means and standard deviations are indicated [30]. Fiber alignment indicated in bars; parallel to the applied stress direction results in 100-fold increase in strength. (c) Strengths of single network hydrogels as a function of applied displacement rate; medians (approximate means) and ranges indicated. Increasing displacement rate 100-fold increases median strength by about a factor of 2.